

ASSESSMENT OF ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AMONG SELECTED STUDENTS OF ARTS AND SCIENCE COLLEGE AT PUDUCHERRY

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Abstract

INTRODUCTION Academic procrastination is common yet universal phenomenon among the college students. It gives bad outcome of people life when they delaying their work. Student should know the importance of educational task during their academic and has to understand their responsibility in student life. **OBJECTIVE** The aim of the study to find the association between the academic procrastination and socio demographic variables, attendance percentage and academic performance of undergraduate arts and science college students. **METHODOLOGY** Descriptive cross sectional method study was designed to collect data from 369 students by using convenience sampling technique. Tuckman procrastination scale was used to collect the data. Descriptive and inferential statistics (Kruskal Wallis, Mann Whitney U test) were used to analyze the data. Analysis was carried out in SPSS version 22.0 (SPSS-Statistical Package for Social Science version 22.0). **RESULTS** The result of the study showed that the mean of academic procrastination scores found to be 44.66 ± 11.64 . It also indicates that students were having higher level of procrastination. With regard to association, the course of study, number of friends and attendance percentage were having significant association with academic procrastination at $p < 0.05$. **CONCLUSION** The study concluded that undergraduate arts and science students were having higher level of academic procrastination (mean 44.66 ± 11.64). Students needs guidance and counseling services to overcome academic procrastination.

Keywords: Academic Procrastination, Undergraduate, Tuckman Procrastination Scale

INTRODUCTION

Any intended course of action that results in unsatisfactory performance and emotional upset, which is an irrational delay yet voluntary is defined as Procrastination.¹ Procrastination is a common human characteristic but it gives bad outcome to people's life. Procrastinators can be fired from jobs and can lose communication with their significant acquaintances because they have a problem to finish their duty on time. As they don't fulfill their responsibilities repeatedly, they have a tendency to feel undermining of their self-confidence, convincing them that they are lazy and worthless.

Procrastination negatively affects many aspects of a person's life like success or accomplishments, when the person prefers to put things off or delay duties instead of completing tasks or assignments.² Academic procrastination is a common yet universal phenomenon among the college students. Procrastination in academic education and training means all the delay in academic activities which may be affecting learning and achievement and are intentional incidental and/or habitual. Slowing down of student's performance, carelessness, laziness, academic stagnation and irresponsibility are most common effects of procrastination.³ Procrastination in academics may be because due to lack of motivation, deficiencies in self-regulation, disorganization and poor time management, poor study skill, inability to concentrate can result in delaying the academic's work. To reduce the procrastination a proper guidance and counselling division of work and provide motivation to the student can help to manage the academic procrastination.⁴ It is a wide spread phenomenon with approximately 30%-60% with undergraduate students report regularly postponing educational tasks—writing assignments, studying for exam, reading weekly assignments to the point at which optimal performance becomes unlikely.⁵ Occasionally delay may be acceptable but what distinguishes problematic or habitual procrastination from mere indecisiveness to do an activity is the external subjective discomfort.⁶

OBJECTIVES

To assess the level of academic procrastination among undergraduate students of selected arts and science college.

To identify the association between the academic procrastination and socio demographic variables, attendance percentage and academic performance of undergraduate arts and science college students.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

For the current study, quantitative approach, Cross sectional descriptive methodology was used. The sampling population for the study includes all the undergraduate (2nd & 3rd year) students belongs to Commerce, arts and science group those who are studying in selected arts and science college, Puducherry. 389 undergraduate students were included those who met the inclusion criteria. The non-probability convenience sampling was used to collect the data for the participants. Sample size was estimated using statistical formula for estimating the sample size for single proportion. The expected proportion of students' academic procrastination is 0.50 (50%) and the sample size was estimated at 5% level of significance and 5% relative precision. The instrument used for the data collection consists of socio-demographic proforma and Tuckman Procrastination scale to assess the level of procrastination. After the data collection, the data analysis was done using descriptive (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Kruskal-Wallis's test, Mann Whitney U test).

RESULT

Table1: Socio-demographic profile of study participants. (N=389)

Variables	Categories	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age in years	18	5	1.3%
	19	61	15.7%
	20	163	41.9%
	21	135	34.7%
	22	25	6.4%
Course	Commerce	79	20.3%
	Arts	125	32.1%
	Science	185	47.6%
Year of study	2 nd year	172	44.2%
	3 rd year	217	55.8%
Place of stay	Hostel	39	10%
	Home	350	90%
Hobbies	Sports	59	15.2%
	Music	91	23.4%
	Drawing	73	18.8%
	Cooking	24	6.2%
	Reading	74	19%
No of friends	0-5	134	34.4%
	5-10	139	35.7%
	11-15	43	11.1%
	>15	73	18.8%
Types of family	Joint	132	33.9%
	Nuclear	257	66.1%
Parental status	Living together	346	88.9%
	Separate	32	8.2%
	Divorced	11	2.8%
Attendance percentage	70-80	61	15.7%
	81-90	157	40.4%
	91-100	171	44%
Academic performance (%)	50-60	16	4.1%
	61-70	87	22.4%
	71-80	162	41.6%
	81-90	119	30.6%
	91-100	5	1.3%

Figure1: Distribution of course among the study participant

Figure 2: Distribution of academic procrastination

The mean score of academic procrastination was found to be 44.66 ± 11.63 . The results also indicated that students were having higher level of procrastination.

Table 2: Association between academic procrastination and socio demographic variables (N=389)

Variables	Categories	Median (Q1,Q3)	Kruskal-Wallis H/Mann-whitneyU Test	P Value
Age in years	18	41.00(40.00,44.50)	8.95	0.06
	19	39.00(36.00,45.50)		
	20	38.00(38.00,48.00)		
	21	35.00(35.00,54.00)		
	22	34.00(34.00,48.00)		
Course	Commerce	41.00(36.00,43.00)	12.79	0.02*
	Arts	41.00(37.00,46.00)		
	Science	44.00(36.00,61.00)		
Year of study	2 nd Year	41.00(38.00,46.00)	17806.00	0.43
	3 rd year	42.00(36.00,58.00)		
Place of stay	Hostel	43.00(37.00,63.00)	5575.00	0.60
	Home	42.00(36.00,47.00)		
Hobbies	Sport	41.00(36.00,45.00)	3.09	0.68
	Music	42.00(38.00,47.00)		
	Drawing	42.00(36.50,52.00)		
	Cooking	41.00(35.25,45.75)		
	Reading	42.00(36.00,47.25)		
	Others	42.00(36.00,61.75)		
No. of friends	0-5	41.00(36.00,47.00)	11.82	0.08*
	11-15	43.00(40.00,50.00)		
	>15	40.00(36.00,43.50)		
Types of family	Joint	41.00(36.00,46.75)	14956.50	0.05
	Nuclear	42.00(37.00,48.50)		
Parental status	Living Together	42.00(36.75,48.00)	0.23	0.89
	Separate	43.00(36.00,50.75)		
	Divorced	40.00(38.00,45.00)		
Attendance percentage	70-80	43.00(38.00,47.00)	13.66	0.01*
	81-90	43.00(36.00,45.00)		
	91-100	41.00(36.00,45.00)		
Academic performance	50-60	38.50(36.00,46.75)	4.39	0.35
	61-70	42.00(36.00,47.00)		
	71-80	42.00(37.00,47.25)		
	81-90	41.00(42.50,64.00)		
	91-100	49.00(42.50,64.00)		

*S-Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

The association between the academic procrastination and socio-demographic variables is showed in table 2. The academic procrastination was found to have an association with courses, of friends, attendance percentage at $p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

A total of 389 participants who were present in the college during the time of data collection were included in the study. The instrument used for the data collection consists of socio-demographic proforma and Tuckman Procrastination scale to assess the level of procrastination. Participants were selected using convenience sampling technique based on the inclusion criteria. A total of 389 2nd and 3rd year undergraduate students were included in the study. After the data collection, the data analysis was done using descriptive (frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential statistics (Kruskal-Wallis test, Mann WhitneyU test).

The association of level of procrastination with demographic variables was found to be significant for (course of study, number of friends, attendance percentage at ($p < 0.05$). Science students have the significant higher association in academic procrastination. Students with 5-15 friends are having more tendencies to procrastinate academic requirements. Students with higher level of attendance are less tends to do procrastination than who are having lesser level of attendance.

The majority of the subjects belonged to the age of 19 (163, 41.9%) years. In course of study, 79 (20.3%) of the subjects belonged to commerce, 125 (32.1%) belonged to arts and 185 (47.6%) belonged to science.

CONCLUSION

Procrastination is the voluntary postponement of an unpleasant task, often against one's better judgment. It can be situational or chronic. Students usually procrastinate due to being perfectionist, dreamer, defer, over doer or crisis maker. It does not create always poorer performances but also mental health will be affected because nothing is ever perfect, students will feel anxious and stressed — which may ultimately lead you to depression. However Students can stop procrastination by develop a structured work on their own accountability, not to avoid unpleasant works, letting go the unnecessary perfectionism, finishing work without seeing the deadline.

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